

PROSPECTS FOR THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF GEORGIA AND THE IMPORTANCE OF ENERGY AND TRANSPORT POTENTIALS

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Abstract

The South Caucasus region has the potential to become a major economic hub, but it faces a number of challenges, including: Lack of regional cooperation: The three countries in the region - Georgia, Azerbaijan, and Armenia - have a history of conflict and mistrust. This has hindered cooperation on economic issues, such as trade, transportation, and energy; Inefficient institutions: The institutions in the South Caucasus are often weak and inefficient. The region has a young and growing population, and it is located at a strategic crossroads between Europe and Asia. With the right policies, the South Caucasus can become a prosperous and stable region. The document discusses a number of specific initiatives that could help to promote economic growth in the South Caucasus. These include: Building a new transport corridor: The construction of a new transport corridor linking the South Caucasus with Europe and Asia would boost trade and investment; Developing the tourism industry: The South Caucasus is a beautiful and historic region with a lot to offer tourists.

Keywords: Energy sector, Transport sector, Economic development, Georgian Economy

Introduction

The future of the South Caucasus is impossible to imagine without the stability and prosperity of all three states in the region. (Anguridze et al., 2015). This requires a common vision of the region as a stable and functionally integrated region, where all three states closely cooperate to build balanced and mutually beneficial internal cooperation and act from a single coordinated position in foreign policy (Gupta, Sharma, 2021; (Sinha, Singh, 2021), based on pragmatic considerations. This automatically excludes confrontational approaches to working with major political players in world politics, as well as a deep understanding of geopolitics, the essential interests of major players, the identification of areas of competition, contradictions, and the lines of confrontation (Babajani and Shahhosseini, 2021).

The biggest problems in the South Caucasus arose when the three countries of the South Caucasus did not understand or made mistakes in assessing the geopolitical interests of the main players in world politics. This happened 100 years ago and again in the 1990s. The rivalry of the main players in world politics has an impact on current political events in the region. This influence was clearly manifested in the events of the region in recent years.

Our main idea is that the three states of the South Caucasus should act in a coordinated manner in political matters (Bartosiewicz, Czinkota, 2016), based on the understanding that together they can achieve much greater results for their countries than if they acted separately and played on different sides. As for the economy, the South Caucasus should be seen as a single economic space, without any customs restrictions, with mutual agreements in place that allow goods and capital to move freely under agreed regimes, etc (Cai, Zhang, 2022). This would benefit not only the countries of the region, but also their neighbors and the wider region. Only in this way can we achieve peace in the region, where people can move freely, where there are guarantees that the region is not a threat, and where the three countries do not engage in zero-sum political games.

The South Caucasus should become a profitable platform for negotiations, settlement of disputes and disagreements.

States can only achieve mutually beneficial cooperation and prosperity if they resolve the issue of mutual security guarantees (Dash, 2022; Gautam, 2022). For the countries of our region, the biggest political mistake would be to play dangerous political games with one of the sides in world politics, as this could lead to the loss of statehood for one or all three states of the South Caucasus.

The purpose of this article is to acquaint readers with the special opportunities for the development of the Georgian economy and the role of the transport and energy system in this development, as well as the mutual relations between the states of the South Caucasus.

The implementation of the planned program can make a significant contribution to the increase in both the size and competitiveness of the Georgian economy in the medium term (Anguridze et al., 2015; Lashkhi, 2017; Sikharulidze, 2018). The idea is simple: Georgia can gain a qualitatively greater economic benefit by using its geopolitical position more efficiently. The scale of the ongoing projects goes far beyond the borders of one country and provides an excellent opportunity for neighboring countries (Chochia et al., 2018; 2020; Gamsakhurdia et al, 2017), especially Azerbaijan and Armenia. This is especially important for Armenia, which has been experiencing difficulties with transport links to the outside world for years. Recent events have allowed this country to expand its capabilities and connect to new transport networks, a process that has essentially already begun.

Energy and Transport Sector in Georgia

There is no doubt that deep economic integration, the exchange of opportunities and resources, will have a positive impact on the economies of these countries. A comparative analysis of the economies of these countries leads to this conclusion (see Figure 1. All data are expressed in constant 2015 prices, in US dollars). In Georgia, the maximum GDP level was reached in 1985

and amounted to 21.935 billion US dollars. By 1990, the GDP of Azerbaijan amounted to 20.239 billion US dollars, Georgia - 17.029 billion dollars, and Armenia - 5.84 billion dollars. The next four years saw the largest economic decline in Georgia - 363.1%; in Azerbaijan the decline was 238.9% (1995) and in Armenia 213.5%

(1993). Since then, the economies of Georgia and Armenia have grown at very low rates, lagging behind those of Azerbaijan, which has grown strongly since 2004.

Picture. 1. GDP of Azerbaijan, Georgia and Armenia at constant 2015 prices in US dollars (Georgia data from 1965, and Azerbaijan and Armenia data from 1990).

Source: World Bank national accounts data.

Before the pandemic (2019), the GDP of Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Armenia was \$53.613 billion, \$17.758 billion, and \$12.876 billion, respectively. In 2020, this figure was \$51.307 billion, \$16.557 billion, and \$11.915 billion.

It is noteworthy that relations between the two states have been interrupted since the early 1990s. The range of relations between Georgia and Azerbaijan is mainly limited to the import of energy carriers, plastic products, furniture, and building materials. Georgia exports cement, locomotives (small), railway devices, chemical products, mineral waters, alcoholic beverages, and pharmaceutical products to Azerbaijan. There are few joint ventures, mutual investments, and trade and economic relations between the two countries (Charaia, Lashkhi, 2020a; 2020b; 2021). This situation hides a huge potential that will be revealed after the settlement of conflicts and the building of mutually beneficial and pragmatic relationships.

In the medium and especially long term, an active policy is imperative for the economic development of Georgia. This policy should aim to ensure stable economic growth by gradually changing the structure of exports and, in the long term, the structure of production. This can be achieved through the rational and productive development of available resources and the strengthening of the innovative component of the development of the economy. In the next decade, the gradual transfer of the Georgian economy to innovative rails is an urgent task.

There are sectors and industries in the Georgian economy that have the potential to be competitive in both domestic and international markets (Gamsakhurdia, Fetelava, 2023; Kvirikvaia et al., 2018; Zivzivadze et al., 2021). However, in order to realize these competitive advantages, an appropriate state policy and the development of market institutions and mechanisms are

required. At this stage, the conditions that have developed in these competitive sectors do not yet contribute to the expansion of production, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI), and modernizing the production base. As a result, the efficiency of these sectors is low.

The main direction of the state structural policy should be to increase the competitiveness of the Georgian economy in order to achieve the following interrelated tasks:

1. Develop a private sector that is competitive in domestic and foreign markets. This will involve supporting and ensuring the success of Georgian companies in foreign markets and carrying out structural changes to increase the share of industries that produce (or will produce) products with a higher degree of processing, as well as the development of service industries.
2. Correct structural deformations that have accumulated over 30 years. This will involve developing new innovative sectors and gradually eliminating inefficient and unprofitable industries.
3. Transform low-performing institutions of the economy. These institutions are especially important for development and determine the direction of the process of transition to market principles. Examples of such institutions include commodity and financial markets, the structure of state ownership, and the system of state regulation. These institutions function inefficiently due to a poorly conceived modernization policy and errors in its implementation.
4. Accelerate the development and restructuring of the entire economic system and functioning markets in the process of economic transformation.

One of the main tasks of economic policy is to develop human capital by increasing the level of knowledge and intelligence. This task is especially im-

portant to the extent that the economy creates and develops a sector where knowledge is the most important and only factor that ensures development.

The main factors hindering the development of competitive production and the emergence of new innovative areas are:

- Insufficient availability of capital. This has been caused by an artificial reduction in the money supply for years. The monetization coefficient ($M2 / GDP$) did not exceed 0.22 for years. This allowed the monetary authorities to artificially keep the exchange rate of the national currency (Lari) at a very high level. For years, the exchange rate of the US dollar to the Lari was equal to 1.42. Then, for quite a long time, the exchange rate was kept at the level of 1.65 with slight fluctuations around this level. Only in 2014, due to the worsening external circumstances (the economic crisis in the EU, difficulties in Russia, and the war in Ukraine), was it impossible to keep the Lari from depreciating. As a result, the national currency devalued permanently by 32%. Naturally, all these years, the excessively high exchange rate of the national currency did not give incentives for the development of local production and its export orientation.

- Inadequate attraction of FDI. In 2017, FDI showed a sign of growth and amounted to USD 1.9808 billion, which is approximately 12.2% of GDP (USD 16,207.1 billion). However, a country like Georgia needs FDI at the level of 20-25% of GDP. In 2020 and 2021, the volume of FDI was minimal: 572 and 728 million US dollars, respectively.

The weak integration of the Georgian economy into the global economy is not only due to its weak competitiveness, but also to institutional factors, such as the underdeveloped export support infrastructure and the loss of incentives. In this context, the development of naturally existing powerful capabilities in the field of transport and energy is a critical task (Papava, 2014; Wang et al., 2018). Let us consider these possibilities and the ways and directions of their possible development.

1. The development of the transport system aims to achieve two main economic objectives: (1) the growth of the Georgian economy (maximization of income) and (2) the growth of the competitiveness of its economy. These goals can be achieved most efficiently if the transport system develops as the most important transport and logistics hub for a significant part of the Eurasian continent. We can evaluate the growth and development opportunities for the system itself, as well as determine the general parameters for the development of its components.

The transport system of Georgia has a huge potential for growth in export earnings, compared to other sectors of the real economy. This potential is comparable to the potential for innovative development of the Georgian economy.

Georgia's competitiveness is clearly identified in the following areas:

- The time of offer and movement
- The price/tariffs of transportation
- The quality/reliability of transportation

- The ease of administration

Revenue maximization (economic growth) is achieved by moving development towards:

- Georgia as a Hub/Logistics Center
- Priorities by transport types
- Import substitution
- Reserves for cost reduction by sectors

As a result, the full integration of the Georgian transport system into the Eurasian transport system is achieved; the employment of the population of the country is increased; and the environment and human life and health are protected.

To achieve these goals, one of the main projects is the Anaklia transport hub, which is a combination of five main types of transport: sea, air, road, rail, and pipeline. The place of the Georgian transport system is a regional multimodal transport hub, which is connected to regional and internal transport networks. The Anaklia Cargo-Transport Hub is located in the East of Europe, on the coast of the eastern part of the Black Sea in Georgia, in the Zugdidi and Khobi municipalities, in the area of the villages of Anaklia and Khorga, between the Inguri and Khobistskali rivers. The purpose of the node is to provide fast and safe transportation of goods and their services from the West, especially from Europe to the East (Caucasus, Central Asia, China, Korea, Iran, Afghanistan, Pakistan, India) and vice versa, as well as from the North (Russian Federation) to the South (Turkey, Middle East), and vice versa. The node is the basis and will play a major role in the TRACECA.

Comparing today's existing routes for transporting goods from the West to China through the Caucasian transport corridor, it is clear that this is the shortest route. This node also makes it possible to create two new routes: firstly, the Iran-India Caucasus Transport Corridor, and secondly, the Russia-Anaklia Cargo-Transport Hub_ Middle East. Naturally, the appearance in Georgia of such a transport hub, which automatically implies the participation of Azerbaijan, gives Armenia a powerful incentive to connect to it and be part of this largest hub, and the India-Iran Caucasian transport corridor, in all considerations, must pass through Armenia. Such interpenetration of transport systems and their integration into a more powerful international transport system should be of paramount importance for the three states of the South Caucasus.

Such integration into global transport networks also has a very large political burden: it helps to increase the security of countries connected to this system, the openness of the economy, and the efficient use of available potential resources. A reliable and well-established international transport system must function stably, which is possible only in conditions of political stability and predictability of the policy of the governments of the participating countries, in the direction of their continuity and fidelity to their obligations in the long term.

Such a powerful international transport system is of great significance and can attract the attention and interest of the major players in world politics. It can help to resolve the pressing problems that have been affecting Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Armenia for years. The integration of the transport resources of these states

has a broader context: the expansion and interpenetration of the economies of the three countries. This requires the simplification of customs and other regimes that impede the free movement of goods and capital, the harmonization of tariff and tax policies, and, in the long term, the movement towards a single economic space with harmonized legislation and a coordinated economic policy.

The transport hub will serve any type of cargo, including dry cargo, container cargo, Ro-Ro cargo (roll-on/roll-off shipments), rail ferry transportation, liquid cargo (oil and oil products, drinking water, liquefied natural gas (LNG), and others). Cargo transportation will be provided by sea, air, rail, road, and pipelines. The maximum water depth in the access to the sea channel and the internal water area of the port is 18.5 meters. It can receive and serve tankers with a tonnage (in carcass weight) of up to 125,000 tons and gas carriers with a volume of up to 220,000 cubic meters. The port has the ability to simultaneously receive 34 tankers. The port is multifunctional and will serve any type of cargo. Its estimated cargo turnover can be 100-120 million tons per year.

If Georgia is not careful and is too focused on its own interests, it may lose its own transport potential and face a reduction in transit traffic through its territory. The losses could be significant. Everything will depend on the implementation of transport corridors without Georgia's participation. Naturally, Georgia will benefit greatly from regional cooperation.

2. Development of energy. Georgia has a powerful energy potential for the development of its own economy. In 2022-2030, according to generation sources (HPPs and TPS), the dynamics of energy consumption shows that in meeting the demand for electricity, the share of HPPs in 2025 will decrease to 58.5%, and the share of TPS will increase to 41.5%. The strategic calculations of the energy development of Georgia set out the optimal structure of fuel and energy resources, taking into account the requirements of the energy, economic, hydrological, environmental, and socio-economic development of Georgia, taking into account the existing realities.

The energy policy of Georgia at this stage does not sufficiently take into account the interests of the country's economic and social development. An export orientation, rather than an emphasis on the use of produced electricity for the development of domestic production, is generally characteristic of developing countries with a low level of development, and not a country that aspires to strong development. Such a policy cannot be productive and is not characteristic of countries with a high level of development. This policy does not take into account the integration of the electricity supply of the South Caucasus states, which can

lead to significant benefits and increase their efficiency, especially if the South Caucasus countries work in a single system connected by neighboring countries with high energy potential. With such a mode of operation, for the economic, energy, social, and cultural development of Georgia, it is much more profitable not to export electricity as a raw material and to generally emphasize export, but to develop small and medium-sized energy-intensive industries that will contribute to an increase in demand for renewable energy sources (RES), respectively, their development, the growth of employment of the population, and the promotion of cultural development. Specific initiatives for the development of RES are being considered within the framework of a unified state development strategy, which, for its part, is based on the principles of a market economy and transparency. Such a strategy corresponds to the interests of optimal and sustainable development of the country. Everything else will comply with the obligations under the unified energy system, and these obligations are not unilateral.

The real opportunities for Georgia's socio-economic development are functionally dependent on the generation of electricity and the thoughtful development of the country's existing energy resources. In the conceptual calculations of the country's energy development, strategic conditions are highlighted that contribute to the energy development of Georgia: existing energy capacities, hydropower resources, priority development of hydropower, the possibility of performing the function of an energy corridor in the region, the development of energy saving programs and ways to implement them.

We must look for the prospects for generating electricity in well-thought-out and economically evaluated decisions regarding the energy resources of the country. Based on these considerations, an assessment was made of the country's energy demand until 2025, inclusive (see the attached table). It is noteworthy that the hydropower industry will play a major role in electricity generation, and its development will be given special attention.

A natural question arises: where and how can Georgia, Azerbaijan, and Armenia cooperate in the energy sector? There are many areas of cooperation: first and foremost, the creation of a unified power supply system and the export of electricity to neighboring and nearby countries. This is a promising direction! At this stage, it is necessary to increase energy capacities in accordance with the requirements for the development of their own economies, with the expectation of medium-term prospects and the establishment of mutual interests in order to combine their own energy systems.

Diagram. 1.

Year	Million Kvt.h.	HPP	Current TPS	% HPP	% TPS
2022	14312.3	10287.0	3051.9	71,9	21,3
2023	17400	10460	575	60	40
2024	18000	10660	575	59	41
2025	18575	10860	575	58.5	41.5

Source: Forecast balance of electricity (power). 1922.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Georgia has a number of opportunities to improve its economy, including:

- Developing its transport and energy systems to make it a regional hub for trade and commerce.
- Investing in human capital to create a more skilled workforce.
- Attracting foreign investment to boost economic growth.
- Resolving conflicts with its neighbors to improve regional stability.

If Georgia can successfully implement these reforms, it has the potential to become a prosperous and thriving nation. Here are some additional details about each of these opportunities:

- **Transport and energy:** Georgia is located at a strategic crossroads between Europe and Asia, and its transport and energy infrastructure could be used to facilitate trade and commerce between these two regions. For example, the country is currently building a new deep-sea port in Anaklia that could be used to ship goods to and from Europe and Asia. Additionally, Georgia has significant hydropower resources that could be used to generate electricity for export.
- **Human capital:** Georgia has a young and growing population, and if it can invest in education and training, it can create a more skilled workforce that will be attractive to businesses. For example, the government could provide scholarships for students to study in foreign universities, or create trainings for high-demand industries.
- **Foreign investment:** Foreign investment is essential for economic growth, and Georgia has a number of advantages that could attract foreign investors, including a stable political environment, a low-tax regime, and a skilled workforce. The government could also take steps to make it easier for foreign investors to do business in Georgia.
- **Regional stability:** Georgia is located in a volatile region, and if it can resolve conflicts with its neighbors, it will create a more stable environment for economic growth. For example, the country is currently negotiating a peace agreement with Russia over the status of the breakaway region of Abkhazia. If this agreement is successful, it could open up new opportunities for trade and investment between Georgia and Russia.

These are just some of the opportunities that Georgia has to improve its economy. If the government can successfully implement these reforms, it has the potential to become a prosperous and thriving nation.

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